

inoculum containing about 10^8 cells/ml. Disease intensity was scored after 14 d, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale.

Only RP2151-173-1-8, RP2151-40-1, Kachamota, and DV85 showed resistance to the Aduthurai pathotype (Table 2). □

Field and screenhouse evaluation for resistance to rice tungro (RTV)

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We evaluated high-yielding rice varieties and lines for field tolerance to RTV in the 1985 wet season. Infection was scored 30 d after transplanting and field tolerance was scored after flowering.

Varieties and lines scoring 1 to 3 were tested in the screenhouse in the 1986 wet season, with 20 seedlings/variety exposed to either 1 or 5 RTV-viruliferous leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* per seedling. Symptoms were scored and seedlings tested for presence of the bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses by latex serological test. Infection rate and plant height and tiller number reduction were scored visually.

Virippu and Ptb 18 scored 1 in the field but had high infection in the screenhouse (see table). Some varieties showing field tolerance had high infection in the screenhouse. Reduction in height and tiller number was less in varieties with field tolerance score 1 than in varieties with score 3.

Infection with both RTBV and RTSV was low in these varieties. Some had RTBV alone. RTSV infection alone was low (0-10%). Ambemohar 59, BJI, and Gopalbhog were not infected with either virus. Infection and reduction in height and tiller number were higher in plants inoculated at 5 hoppers/ seedling.

Although Utkalprabha and Sabari had high infection in the field, by time of flowering they showed tolerance scores of 2 and 3. □

RTV incidence in rice varieties in the field (1985 wet season) and in a screenhouse test (1986 wet season). Cuttack, India.

	Field		Screenhouse ^b		
	Symptoms (%)	Tolerance score ^a	RTBV+RTSV (%)	RTBV (%)	RTSV (%)
<i>Popular Indian varieties</i>					
Ambemohar 59	0	1	0	0	0
Basmati 370	2	1	0	10	0
Krishnabhog	3	1	0	10	0
Mudgo	0	1	0	10	0
Ptb 18	0	1	0	60	0
Tulsimanjari	2	1	0	10	0
Type 90	2	1	0	20	0
Virippu	6	1	0	30	10
Amaravathi	0	2	10	30	0
BJI	0	2	0	0	0
Gopalbhog	4	2	0	0	0
Pokkali	7	2	10	30	0
Utkalprabha	25	2	20	50	0
Vytilla 2	2	2	10	30	0
White Luchai	5	2	10	20	0
Asha	18	3	10	0	0
Aswathi	3	3	10	20	0
Daya	15	3	10	20	10
Ratna	8	3	0	20	0
Sabari	51	3	10	10	0
TN1 (check)	100	9	80	0	0
<i>CRR breeding lines</i>					
CR146-7001	2	1	0	10	0
CR146-7004	15	2	10	20	0
CR260-131-5-713	12	2	10	30	0
CR316-639	6	2	0	20	0
CR365-134	9	2	10	20	0
CR319-644	6	3	10	0	0
CR260-136-321	7	3	10	20	0

^a1 = no visible symptoms; 2 = plants are green, slightly stunted, less than 10% did not flower; 3 = less than 20% did not flower; 9 = plants show orange yellow color, severe stunting, and no flowering.

^bMass inoculation at 5 leafhoppers/seedling. All varieties except two had 0 RTSV: Virippu and Daya had 10% RTSV. LSD for the screenhouse symptoms was 17.83 (0.05) and 24.07 (0.01).

Reactions of Mahsuri and Sona Mahsuri to blast (BI)

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Mahsuri rice covers a substantial area during the Jul-Dec season in Assam

State. But it is highly susceptible to neck BI. We are looking for a variety with Mahsuri-type grain and resistance to neck BI.

Sona Mahsuri (KMS5914-4-6) from the cross Sona/ Mahsuri (released in Karnataka State as Mandya Vijaya), with panicle traits similar to Mahsuri, is moderately resistant to leaf BI. We compared leaf and neck BI reactions of Sona Mahsuri and Mahsuri.

Table 1. Leaf and neck BI reactions^a of Mahsuri and Sona Mahsuri. Assam, India.

Variety	Leaf BI		%	Neck BI	
	Score	Reaction		Score	Reaction
Sona Mahsuri	4	MR	18.1	5	MR
Mahsuri	7	S	97.4	9	HS
Pusa 2-21, susceptible check	8	S	98.5	9	HS

^aMR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.